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'I don't want to completely lose myself': social mobility as movement across classed, ethnicised and gendered spaces.

Abstract

This paper explores how subjective experiences of social mobility are informed by dimensions of identity other than class (e.g. ethnicity, gender). Drawing on in-depth interviews with British-born young women of Bangladeshi Muslim, working-class origins in higher education, I critically interrogate their articulations of class positioning and trajectory and the interplay between participation in education and employment and gendered identities. Findings evidence the multifarious and value-ridden character of class signifiers, the relational nature of class positioning and the entrenchment of middle-classness and whiteness, and testify to the compounding tensions experienced by upwardly mobile individuals of minority ethnic origins. The pursuit of upward mobility through participation in higher education and employment is also shown to entail shifts in gendered expectations and strains in performing valued gendered identities. Ultimately, I argue that social mobility processes are better understood as involving a movement across material and symbolic spaces where markers, dispositions and practices linked to individuals' class, ethnicity, religion and gender acquire differential value. This intersectional lens enables a complex and nuanced picture to emerge, which foregrounds multiple tensions, displacements and resulting inequalities in experiences and outcomes.

Keywords: social mobility; intersectionality; ethnicity; Bangladeshi; subjective experiences

Introduction

In the UK, social mobility has been set as a policy goal at the turn of the century under New Labour and has since been upheld by Coalition and Conservative governments alike (Labour Government 2009; Coalition Government 2011; House of Lords 2016). Mainstream policy discourse has largely centred on the promotion of upward mobility for those from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds, to be achieved primarily through increased education, training and employment opportunities. While popular among policy-makers, the rhetoric of social mobility has been criticised from a sociological perspective for its complicity in legitimising existing hierarchies of value and status, diverting attention from more fundamental questions of social justice and equity, and ultimately perpetuating the inequalities it purports to resolve (Payne 2012; Lawler and Payne 2017). Research has also drawn attention to the psychic costs that mobility can entail as individuals move in and out of different and at times discordant class cultures (Friedman 2013). Yet, sociological literature on subjective experiences of social mobility has so far largely focused on upwardly mobile individuals of white British background. This article aims to expand this focus and provide an enriched understanding of mobility experiences as shaped by intersecting identities and inequalities of ethnicity, race, religion and gender as well as class.

Drawing on in-depth interview data, the paper interrogates the views, experiences and identity articulations of 17 British-born young women of Bangladeshi Muslim, working-class origins attending university in London. Compared to other ethnic groups, men and women of Bangladeshi background experience especially high unemployment and inactivity rates, are

disproportionately concentrated in low-status, low-pay occupations, and under-represented in professional and managerial positions (Nazroo and Kapadia 2013; ONS 2020). The attainment of a higher education (HE) degree is among the main factors affecting the probability of being employed and having a professional or managerial job, especially for women (Clark and Drinkwater 2007). Between 1991 and 2011, the proportion of Bangladeshis aged 16+ with degree-level qualifications has risen from 5% to 20%, with women accounting for around half of this latter percentage (ONS 2011; Lymperopoulou and Parameshwaran 2015). Still, a lower proportion of graduates of Bangladeshi background are employed in professional and managerial jobs compared to the white majority, and low levels of employment and upward mobility tend to persist despite controlling for education (Karlsen et al. 2020; ONS 2020). Focusing for the first time on the interaction between class, gender and ethnicity in employment and pay outcomes, the Social Mobility Commission's 2019 'State of the Nation' report highlights the stark disadvantage experienced by women of Bangladeshi origins.

In what follows, I firstly discuss sociological insights on subjective experiences of upward mobility and argue for the adoption of an intersectional prism of analysis. I then outline the research context and methods before moving to the findings. Empirical findings are structured around two themes: participants' conceptualisations of class and relative positionings, and the relation between upward mobility and gendered expectations and practices. I evidence the multifaceted and value-ridden nature of class signifiers, the relational character of class identification and distinction, and the entrenchment of class, race, ethnicity and religion in lived experiences and imaginaries. In so doing, I illuminate the role of the interplay among these dimensions of identity and inequality in shaping possibilities for identification and the tensions involved in this process. Regarding gender, I show how the valuing of education and socio-economic betterment was linked to changes in gendered norms about marriage, living arrangements and the role of women in the family. I also highlight the tensions generated by mobility with respect to gendered identities and dispositions, as these women perceived a misfit between high-status university and employment environments and valued performances of femininity. In sum, findings show how upwardly mobile individuals move across material and symbolic spaces where differential value is attributed to markers, dispositions and practices that are linked to one's gender, class, race, ethnicity and religious faith. For the women of Bangladeshi background who took part in this study, this could generate changes in outlooks and practices as well as tensions, a sense of displacement and a preoccupation with 'not losing oneself'.

Upward mobility, identities and inequalities

Social mobility processes have been examined, since the 1990s, by a growing body of literature adopting a qualitative methodological approach and often drawing on Bourdieu's conceptual framework to expose the interplay of social structures and culture in shaping unequal trajectories. Focusing on the lived experiences of upwardly mobile individuals, these studies evidence how class does not merely indicate a position in the labour market but instead becomes part of one's subjectivity, as it is internalised and expressed through classed dispositions and embodied cultural capital (Bourdieu 1984). Lawler's (1999) analysis of upwardly mobile women's narratives shows for example how the possession of certain tastes and dispositions can be considered more important than a given job or income in denoting class. Social mobility does therefore not simply entail a movement from one occupational category to another, 'but involves processes of detachment from, and attachment to, particular class cultures' (Friedman 2013).

Different and at times incompatible class cultures also mark the contexts where socially mobile individuals engage and are socialised (Bourdieu 1998, 2004). This can generate tensions and contradictions, including feelings of unease, shame and insecurity, and a sense of 'cultural homelessness' (Freidman 2012) as the individual combines dispositions attached to different class cultures and precisely because of this never finds itself 'as a fish in water' (Bourdieu and Wacquant 1992). Studies like those of Reay et al. (2009a, 2009b), Ingram (2011, 2018), and Abrahams and Ingram (2013) highlight the complex identity work performed by those who engage in contexts characterised by different class cultures. They show how 'educationally successful' working-class students respond in different ways to the newly encountered context, from detachment to immersion, and how their social and learner identities are modified, reinforced or transformed by participation in education. Even when they appear to adapt, this involves considerable distress. Friedman and Laurison's (2019) research on elite professions further demonstrates the importance of this ill-fit with the institution's class-based culture in explaining socio-economic inequalities in progression and pay. Contrary to dominant policy framings of upward mobility as an unproblematic transition from lower to higher socio-economic positions, characterised in exclusively positive terms, these readings bring home the costs of mobility for individuals' subjectivities and related inequalities in experiences and outcomes.

This strand of literature has primarily focused on unveiling the role of social class background in informing subjective experiences of social mobility and producing unequal outcomes. Yet, other dimensions of identity and inequality, such as gender, race, ethnicity and religious faith, also influence experiences and outcomes in distinctive and crucial ways. Studies on young peoples participation in education cast light, for example, on the ways in which dispositions and capital are shaped by gender and ethnicity as well as class (Lareau and Horvat 1999; Archer and Francis 2007; Archer et al. 2013, 2014). They reveal how the interplay of these dimensions generates multiple, complex forms and differential degrees of (mis-)fit relative to specific contexts, which contribute to explain unequal experiences of education and labour market decision-making (Ball et al. 2002; Scandone 2017, 2018).

This article builds on these insights and advances the understanding of subjective experiences of upward mobility by taking an intersectional approach to their analysis. According to Crenshaw (2000, cit. in Lutz 2014), who coined the term,

intersectionality is a conceptualization of the problem that attempts to capture both the structural and dynamic consequences of the interaction between two or more axes of subordination. It specifically addresses the manner in which racism, patriarchy, class oppression and other discriminatory systems create background inequalities that structure the relative positions of women, races, ethnicities, classes, and the like.

As a prism for the analysis of social inequalities, it has come to encompass a range of approaches concerned with investigating 'how socially constructed differences and structures of power work at the level of individual experiences, social practices, institutional arrangements, symbolic representations and cultural imaginaries' (Davis 2014). In this paper, the adoption of an intersectional perspective is aimed at evidencing the mutually constitutive character of identities and inequalities of class, race, ethnicity, religion and gender, as they shape and are being shaped by individuals' experiences of social mobility.

The study

This article draws on data from research on the experiences and identities of British-born young women of Bangladeshi origins attending HE in London. The study aimed to identify how class, ethnicity and gender informed HE participation and progression to the labour market. It also examined the meanings and significance assigned to class, ethnicity, nationality and religious faith as identity dimensions. Participants were purposefully recruited based on class background and the status and socio-economic composition of the university attended, to examine the interplay between the two in shaping experiences and outlooks. Data collection involved two rounds of semi-structured interviews with 21 female students aged 18-24, attending a range of undergraduate degrees across the humanities, social sciences and STEM subjects at differently ranked universities.

Participants were of both what according to the income and status generally attached to their parents' occupation can be broadly defined as working- and middle-class backgrounds. This paper focuses on the experiences of those of working-class origins (17 out of 21), as they pursued upward mobility through HE. This broad categorisation encompassed substantial variation. Fathers were employed in both blue-collar and white-collar jobs, for example as construction and factory workers, cab drivers, chefs, tailors, mentors and tutors. Mothers were either housewives (13) or working in low-pay positions in the social and education sectors (3). Almost all parents came from Bangladesh at different points in their lives, except two of the mothers who were born in Britain. Most participants were born and spent their childhoods in the East London borough of Tower Hamlets, a traditional area of settlement for Bangladeshi immigrants and one of the most deprived local authorities in England as measured through the index of multiple deprivation (Eade and Garbin 2002; DCLG 2010). Some had then moved with their parents to Outer London boroughs, reflecting the tendency for upwardly mobile minority ethnic families to move from the inner city to the suburbs (Butler and Hamnett 2011). All participants of working-class background self-identified as Muslim.

The research involved two rounds of interviews. The first explored family background and history of migration, current and childhood area of residence, primary and secondary schooling, university decision-making, friendship networks, and future hopes and expectations over career, marriage and children. The second interview covered social and academic experiences of HE, support from parents and broader social networks, class identification, and reflections on ethnic, national and religious identity. Participants' narratives were analysed thematically across and within cases, to explain how views and experiences relating to pre-identified and emerging themes were informed by participants' characteristics and by one another.

Empirical findings

Class conceptions and positionings

Class positioning was sometimes discussed in the first interview, especially in relation to its influence on educational experiences, and explored in the second interview through more focused questions. Class was generally conceived of as being defined by one's or one's parents' employment and economic position, and/or by their educational credentials. Signifiers and perceived expressions of class included consumption and lifestyle practices, most notably dwelling, neighbourhood of residence and school attended but also leisure activities and food and musical tastes, embodied practices, such as ways of speaking and dressing, and outlooks and values (e.g. attitudes towards education, work and consumption, and views about society

and politics). The differential capacity to transmit educational and economic advantage was also referred to as a key distinction between classes.

The characterisation of spaces and practices as classed was at times interlinked with attributions of value, as adjectives such as 'nice' and 'good' were used to denote middle-class schools, neighbourhoods and places of residence. Bourdieu (1984, 1996) maintains that according to dominant standards, objects, spaces and practices are valued hierarchically, based on the class composition of those who consume, occupy and enact them. Where the arbitrariness of their classed distribution goes unrecognised, they are legitimised as symbolic capital and their deemed worth is made to stick to the person with profound implications for the valuing of self and others (Lawler 2005). Shay's quote illustrates this point. Like other upwardly mobile families of minority ethnic background (Butler and Hamnett 2011), Shay's parents also moved from the inner city of London to the suburbs when she was 11. When asked about her class position, she recounts of a lifestyle improvement she ascribes to having moved:

This [inner city] area it is of the lower class ... that's like the deprived part of London, so having moved out of there is what helped. ... Once you moved out of there it was like 'okay we are in a nice place now. We have to be nice.' ... Before we used to live here and it wasn't exactly pretty so we never did anything pretty. (Shay)

While Shay refers to an improvement in her family's economic circumstances, her account of upward mobility foregrounds place and habitual practice. Classed practices and spaces are interpreted as being not merely a reflection of one's economic capacity, but value-ridden 'ways of being'. What participants identified as (white) middle-class attitudes could also have negative connotations (e.g. sense of entitlement, racism). However, in contrast to those attributed to the working classes and minority ethnic groups, these attitudes can be seen as stemming from and contributing to reproduce a position of privilege rather than disadvantage.

The women who took part in this research constructed and presented their class positionings and trajectories in relation to these loaded, multifaceted signifiers of class, asserting their identification with some and distinction from others in complex, nuanced and at times contradictory ways. Their self-identification relied not only on their and/or their parents' economic position and education, but also on dominant representations and lived experiences of classed outlooks and practices, to which discourses of (de-)attachment and (non-)belonging primarily referred. This is evident in Chandi's articulation of her classed identity. Here, the presentation of self as being working-class and becoming middle-class through the achievement of a university degree and graduate employment is far from straightforward. Dominant derogatory representations of working-classness and the entrenchment of middle-classness with white Britishness make identification with these categories problematic and fraught with tensions. To reconcile them, Chandi selectively adopts and refuses specific class signifiers, i.e. defines the boundaries and content of her working-classness and eventual middle-classness relative to what it is not:

I am working-class, but I don't feel like I have working-class attitudes and values. Because working-class values are money and success but I'm focusing on my education. ... There's a negative sort of label to working-class people. ... Have you heard of the term chav? I wouldn't associate myself with that. And also the way I speak, I don't use slang all the time. ... Also I'm not ignorant I don't like to stereotype races. Because they say working-class people lack education, but I feel middle-class people also lack education ... they get the news from the media so they put negative labels on us. ... I think I'll be middle-class in the future in terms of my income. My values, what I teach my kids may be working-class. I want them still to work hard, I want them to work for what they get. ... I do want to make it easier for them but only in terms of income, I guess that would make me middle-class, but my values, my Bengali cultural and religious values will still stay the

same. I don't want to completely lose myself. ... Middle-class I just feel like the values is quite different. ... It's more English I think, more British. (Chandi)

Chandi's narrative points to the ambivalence of class signifiers and to the existence of differing representations of the working and middle classes, with some having more respectability than others and working-class respectability being especially predicated on values and attitudes of hard work (Skeggs 1997; Archer 2012; Abrahams 2017).

Chandi's account also highlights how race, ethnicity and religious faith are part of class constructions and distinctions. Reflecting the racialised composition of the British middle class, Chandi sees 'proper' middle-class culture to include white British cultural features. This characterisation of the middle-class location as white was also present in other women's narratives and could problematise identification (see also Archer 2012; Rollock et al. 2013). Similarly to other participants, Chandi stresses the desire to retain her working-class and 'Bengali cultural and religious values' and not to 'completely lose [her]self'. Bourdieu's notion of habitus helps to explain this tension between becoming middle-class and retaining one's ethnic and religious identity. Habitus is for Bourdieu (1977, 2004) 'a socialised subjectivity', an embodied schemata of 'perception, appreciation and action' which derives from the internalisation of collective and individual classed experiences and generates practices in line with those experiences. As well as by class, habitus is also informed by other dimensions of social identity and inequality including race, ethnicity, religion and gender (Lareau and Horvat 1999; Reay 1995; Barrett 2010). Where what is legitimised as middle-class habitus is formed from a specific (white) racialised position and incorporates elements of whiteness, for those of minority ethnic origins the experience of upward mobility is likely to generate strains in maintaining not only one's working-class identity, but also one's ethnic and religious identity.

Participants' experiences of 'moving up' involved moving through classed, racialised and gendered material as well as symbolic spaces, such as universities and courses of study. For Reay et al. (2009a, 2009b), HE institutions also have a habitus, which includes wealth and status, organisational practices, curriculum offer, expectations of students and more subtle cultural and expressive characteristics. Crozier et al. (2008) point additionally to the existence of 'subject sub-cultures' within institutions. These authors evidence how students from different 'socio-cultural locations' (i.e. class, gender, age and ethnicity) experience different extents of fit and adaptation between their habitus, encompassing social and learner identities, and that of the institution. Similarly to the individual habitus, university and subject habitus are also inflected by race, ethnicity, religion and gender as well as class (Scandone 2017). Findings from this research show how different degrees of fit and adaptation between individual and institutional habitus also arise in relation to race, ethnicity, religion and gender. For socially mobile young people of minority ethnic origins in predominantly white, middle-class institutions, the tensions experienced as they 'move up' derive not only from discordant individual and institutional class habituses, but also from a mis-fit related to these other dimensions of identity. Chiming with the accounts of other women in pre-'92 (generally higher status) institutions, Megh's words illustrate how classed and ethnicised processes of fitting inform feelings of (dis)comfort and insecurity, practices of exclusion and self-exclusion and the shape of social networks (see also Tarabini and Curran 2019; Romito et al. 2020):

When I first got here I thought I had made a mistake by choosing it over [university with high % of students of minority ethnic background]. ... I was used to talking in front of everyone before, but when I came here it was a completely new war-game because everyone was more intelligent. ... I thought if I was at [other university] maybe it would have been easier, just because people there would be Asian and it would be easier to kind of like, I don't know whether it is when you feel confident with, I don't want to say 'your own kind'. But at the same time I wanted to meet different people from different places. (Megh)

Finding oneself as a fish out of water is therefore not only a matter of class, and multiple habitus cleavages can arise in relation to different dimensions of identity.

The intent to improve their socio-economic position by participating in HE was voiced by all participants of working-class background. The widely adopted discourse of 'Bangladeshis valuing education and striving to achieve a better life' served for them as a counter-narrative to dominant constructions of working-classness, thus aiding the presentation of an 'educationally / social mobility oriented' sense of self and the take-up of HE (Scandone 2018). The desire to improve their chances to secure a career (intended as a job providing financial stability and opportunities for progression) was expressed alongside a range of views around the influence of class and ethnic background on educational experiences and outcomes. One perception was that class did not affect opportunities:

I don't think [class] matters to be honest, like when you are university, when you are with everyone, no one takes into consideration, no one cares. ...

What about when you leave university?

... I didn't know it mattered. I thought everyone's going to be like everyone at uni. No one cares about stuff like that. Everyone is accepting. (Fauzia)

Another view was that while class informed relative privilege and disadvantage, the class structure was fluid and offered opportunities for social mobility. Whilst acknowledging the favourable impact that a higher-class background can have on life chances, for example, Jamila considered class to be of declining importance as a marker of identity and was confident in her possibilities of achieving 'a good job' irrespective of her parents' position. Her faith in HE as a promoter of socio-economic advancement resonates with the accounts of all of those interviewed, although variation existed in the degree to which they thought this was possible.

Right now I'd probably say working-class and maybe in the future middle-class, but I don't think it has any relevance or importance anymore. I mean I'd say that you know there is the middle-class and there's the upper class and they might have better, you know, so I am contradicting myself. ... I feel like it's a lot more fluid than before, so you can very easily move up the class structure in a sense, but I don't know if that's something we should continue to define ourselves by. (Jamila)

Finally, there were those who stressed the differential (dis)advantage deriving from different class backgrounds and the related resources that one could access:

Middle class people can easily afford [a tutor] whereas I can't really afford one. I have to work hard. ... Placing myself as working class, means that I work harder and they sort of had this served on a plate to them through their parents but I don't have that ... I'm starting here, they are over there. (Chandi)

Understanding how the disadvantage experienced at an individual and group level is related to existing structural inequalities and hierarchies of power can help to move away from societal and internalised perceptions of deficit. For participants to this research, HE participation appeared to contribute to this awareness, which was also expressed in relation to the influence of one's minority ethnic and migration background:

A percentage of working-class children are Bengali and they achieve less. ... Now that I'm doing Education Studies ... I'm learning about languages and how it affects, because at the end of the day my first language is not English my first language is Bengali even though I was born here. I could look back to it, I can see that that maybe the reason why I was struggling a little bit. (Pavi)

While the conception of self as socially mobile was common among participants, some perceived middle-classness as a position that could never be fully achieved. Hamida refers to aspects of both her racialised and classed identity to explain why. On the one hand, she points to the difficulties experienced as a woman of working-class background in attaining the 'right' stock of capital characterising the middle-class position, which comprises of a complexity of social and cultural resources that go beyond what can be obtained through participation in HE. On the other, she points to 'skin colour' as compounding these difficulties, as it structures status and material inequalities within and across classes:

I still consider myself working class, even after [getting a degree], because I still feel as if I have to fight for everything to get what I want. ... I think the class system is more to do with white British people, rather than ethnic minorities. ... The class thing is a big deal, but I've got a bigger issue to deal with. ... However much you educate yourself you still have that accent of being from a working-class background, you won't have every single network, you will still have to fight for things. ...

What do you think in terms of your children ...

Well my nephews, you know what, they are going to get a lot more better advice. ... Pushing them to do like things that will help them on the CV once they start, you know, thinking about going to uni and what they want to do. ...

Why do you say that it's still going to be different than for the white British middle-class?

After getting all that advice? Because of their skin colour. (Hamida)

For Hamida, class system and locations are not straightforwardly applicable to those of minority ethnic origins, as racialised disadvantage prevents from benefitting in the same way from investment in recognised cultural capital. Her account evidences how, for those who are placed in a subordinated racialised location, racial discrimination compounds the tensions experienced by upwardly mobile individuals in achieving and comfortably inhabiting middle-classness.

Social mobility and the negotiation of gendered norms

The women interviewed for this study all stressed the intention to graduate from university and secure a career before getting married. Attaining a HE degree and being employed were considered crucial for ensuring financial security, personal gratification and autonomy. Participants observed how this prospect was shared and supported by their parents. The pursuit of education and professional employment provided a space for them to re-negotiate established gendered norms, as for marriage being postponed to an older age, travelling abroad, and living on one's own. This is well illustrated by Shay, who describes her parents' reaction to her intent to move abroad to find employment in her field of studies:

I thought if my parents, the only reason they would let me go [to another country] is if I were to get married first and I was like: 'no way am I going to get married before I secure myself!'. ... But then I asked them and they were like: 'yeah, go, go, go straightaway'. ... I think my dad knows there's a lot of money involved, so he's happy and he wants me to go secure myself. (Shay)

Shay's account resonates with those of other participants, and shows how the acquisition of cultural and economic capital through education and a career could be used as a leverage to re-negotiate their position as women and generate change in the gendered habitus (dispositions and practices).

The desire to have a career alongside a family also informed decisions about who to marry, with a preference for partners who would support this. This evidences how changing expectations around women's participation in employment may be reproduced throughout generations through practices and decision-making in the domestic and affective spheres. In this sense, the women who took part in this research expected to assume gender roles that differed from those of their mothers, who were for the vast majority housewives:

If I don't work I feel quite restless so I need to work and if my husband who is from Bangladesh has that sort of mentality where I won't be able to work or he doesn't think I should work, I don't think I can settle for someone like that. (Farhan)

These changes in gendered expectations and family practices appear embedded in specific configurations of structural opportunities and constraints. Jamila's and Sadia's reflections illustrate how the drive towards participation in HE and having a career is sustained by the perception of these as enabling more 'freedom' within gendered relations and as necessary to ensure the financial means 'to survive':

I think guys have had freedom sort of to do what they want in a sense which girls might not have always had. ... So to gain that sort of freedom and to you know, go past all those restrictions, university would be the way to get ahead in terms of knowledge and education and then go on to get better and bigger jobs. (Jamila)

Within London, like in order to survive ... you need two incomes. So therefore it's like not even a question of can she work, she has to work. ... You need to have that education background if you want to get the best jobs. (Sadia)

Alongside a career, participants also stressed the importance of having a family. This could lead to tensions, as societal norms and labour market structures impose constraints on gendered performances and make the pursuit of high-status jobs difficultly compatible with the take-up of valued roles as wives and mothers. Below, Sadia discusses her expectations and hopes for the future. The lower status she perceives to be accorded in mainstream society to having a family as opposed to a career and indirect experiences of the difficulties that can arise in combining the two, generate pressure and shape decision-making. Her story shows how attempts at reconciling both could involve orienting oneself towards professions that were seen to more easily enable the establishment of a family.

At first I was essentially like, to be successful was to just have a career. And then we did this whole fieldwork week in India ... and we were speaking to actual women how much importance they put into family and yet still having their careers. ... It seems like it's a Western mentality to think it's backwards or it's like career first. ... It was really empowering to think that you can do both and it was nice to know that you shouldn't feel wrong to want to have a family and you shouldn't feel wrong to also have a career. ... That's why I think teaching would be a really good job but because I feel, like I have seen teachers who have that family. Whereas I see people that went into corporate and that kind of line and it's a lot later in life. (Sadia)

Sadia's reflections evidence the constraints on decision-making imposed by the differential value placed by society on gendered roles, and the gendered, as well as racialised and classed, character of possible (mis-)matches between one's habitus and certain employment areas.

Teaching was especially common among the professions considered by participants. In the following quote, Jamila discusses the differing advice received by her mother, who worked as a teaching assistant and encouraged her to take up a teaching job, and her aunt, who has a

PhD degree, had a high-status job in international development and advocated a less common pathway such as journalism. Her account highlights the importance held by the experiences of relevant others, especially parents and family members, in shaping these women's employment decision-making. These classed and gendered experiences contribute to make various options more or less visible and feasible, by providing 'known routes' (Archer and Francis 2007) and informing 'horizons for action' (Hodkinson and Sparkes 1997).

Whilst my aunt would sort of push me to do something that might be a different, so the journalism schemes and so on, my mum is like sort of encouraging me to take up teaching just because it would be easier with the holidays and so on if I had to juggle motherhood with that, do you know what I mean? ... I have two different sides, two different kinds of encouragement in terms of career. (Jamila)

For those who pursued or intended to pursue educational and employment trajectories that were less common among those of similar ethnic, class and gender background, the mis-fit of classed, gendered and racialised dispositions and ways of being they experienced or anticipated could generate a preoccupation with 'losing oneself'. This chimes with Chandi's previously reported intention to retain her 'working-class, Bangladeshi and religious cultural values' whilst becoming 'middle-class by income'. Talking about her experience of studying at a high-status Russell Group university¹ with a predominantly white middle-class student intake, Kanta reflects on the challenges of fitting in as she considers herself not as career orientated as the majority of students. Her account illustrates the internal conflict that this can generate, as fitting in would mean changing her ways of being and becoming 'not [...] the sort of person [she] wants to be'.

I'm not as career orientated as most students [at my university] are, I'm not interested in investment banking or any of that. So it's been quite challenging in that sense of trying to fit into the environment, but also I'm worried that if I do I'll get lost and not be the sort of person I want to be. (Kanta)

According to Bourdieu (1990, 2005), while habitus always retains a certain inertia, it is also malleable and (re)shaped by socialisation in different environments. Where socialisation takes place in environments characterised by different class cultures and over prolonged periods of time, the individual's habitus may come to incorporate elements of such distinctive cultures (Bourdieu 2004; Ingram 2018). These women's narratives show how these processes are also shaped by other dimensions of social identity such as gender and ethnicity. They additionally highlight the violence of certain (classed, gendered and ethnicised) dispositions being valued more than others, as being successful requires adapting to the dominant norm and abandoning aspects of identity.

Jamila's considerations on her jobs aspirations and desire to find an environment where she is 'able to be [her]self', illustrates these dynamics further:

For me I guess it's being able to be myself. ... Feeling comfortable in an environment that I would guess would be predominantly white male middle-class, because some of those jobs I mentioned will basically be those kind of people. ... I would like to be able to grow and develop, but not have to change myself as a whole. ... I'd like my position as a woman not to be undermined. But also as an 'ethnic minority' ... I wouldn't want to be put on a,

¹ The Russell Group is an organisation that represents 24 top-ranking, research intensive UK universities, with a widespread reputation for academic excellence

not on a lower pedestal but just I wouldn't want to be undermined again just because there are, you know, white male middle-class people in the same jobs or something.

Do you think that might be the case?

I don't think it would be the case. I guess if you let yourself be treated like that then, but if you go in sure of your own position, your own status, I guess then you will be absolutely fine because you are both capable of doing the same job which is why you got the position. And I don't think people are like that I suppose, I would like to think people aren't cheating. (Jamila)

Jamila's words illuminate the strains and contradictions permeating the upwardly mobile trajectories of women and people of minority ethnic background. In explaining her concerns, Jamila refers to the potential discrimination she feels she might face as a woman of minority ethnic - and I would suggest of working-class - origins. Yet, when prompted on whether she thinks this might happen, she ends up downplaying the risk and shifting the responsibility on the individual for 'letting themselves be treated like that'. Her account shows how the differential value that is commonly attributed to gendered, racialised and classed dispositions, reflected and compounded by the underrepresentation in certain employment sectors of people 'like us', can generate tensions between the pursuit of upward mobility and the desire to maintain one's sense of identity. It also illustrates how the subtlety of implicit discrimination based on arbitrary hierarchies of value that reflect pre-existing structures of power can lead to employment inequalities being mis-recognised as individual deficit.

Conclusions

Drawing on the narratives of British-born young women of Bangladeshi working-class origins in HE, this article evidenced the inextricability of class, ethnic, religious and gender identities and inequalities, and the need to consider their interplay in explaining subjective experiences and outcomes of social mobility. Similarly to findings from other studies (Lawler 1999; Archer 2012; Rollock et al. 2013), class location was defined by 'ways of being', including embodied expressions, outlooks and values, as well as by material properties such as employment, educational credentials and income. Participants' reflections highlight the multifaceted, value-ridden and relational character of class constructs and (dis)identification, and the complex boundary work involved in class self-positioning. The racialisation of class identities and entrenchment of middle-classness and whiteness could make middle-class positioning especially problematic. Foregrounding the cultural and affective dimensions of class, critical studies on class inequalities have shown the identity struggles involved in experiences of social mobility (Lawler 1999; Reay et al. 2009a, 2009b; Friedman 2013; Ingram 2018). The findings presented here point additionally to the inter-relation of class, race, ethnicity and religious faith as cross-cutting and mutually constitutive dimensions of identity and inequality, thus drawing attention to the compounding tensions experienced by upwardly mobile individuals of minority ethnic origins. In participants' imaginaries, these dimensions were often co-constructed, and perceptions of middle-classness involved outlooks, values and practices racialised as white. Racial discrimination further undermined the possibility, for those of minority ethnic origins, to fully inhabit the legitimised middle-class location.

Shifting gendered roles both underlay and emerged out of participation in university and employment. In line with other research with young women of South Asian heritage in the UK (Basit 1997; Dwyer and Shah 2006; Bagguley and Hussain 2016), findings show how parents'

valuing of education and professional employment could enable a re-negotiation of established gendered norms. They also illustrate how changing expectations around women's participation in the labour market may be reproduced intergenerationally through domestic and affective practices. Societal differential valuing of gendered roles and labour market structures appeared to constrain employment decision-making and identities, as having a family could be considered difficultly compatible with the pursuit of high-status jobs. Gender and class both contribute to inform this decision-making, as they provide exposure to different pathways through the experiences of relevant others. Finally, findings draw attention to how the pursuit of trajectories that were less common among those of similar ethnic, class and gender background could generate tensions and preoccupations with 'losing oneself'. This was due to an experienced or anticipated mis-fit of classed, gendered and racialised dispositions in institutional environments where the norm was white, male and middle-class and such were valued and legitimised bodies, dispositions and ways of being.

Throughout this article, I have shown how upward mobility involves a movement across material and symbolic spaces where individuals from different backgrounds are unequally represented and differential value is attributed to classed, ethnicised and gendered dispositions and practices. This can generate changes in outlooks and behaviours as well as tensions and a multiplex sense of displacement, thus impacting on perceptions of self, lived experiences and prospects. Bourdieu's relational theory of practice can help us make sense of these processes and 'do' intersectional analysis, that is, explain how multiple intervening dimensions of structural inequality (e.g. gender, race, ethnicity and religious faith) affect social mobility experiences and outcomes. Similarly to class, these other dimensions may also be conceptualised as 'relational ontological spaces' (Anthias 1998), where individuals and 'groups' are hierarchically positioned with respect to each other according to the type and amount of resources held. Bourdieu's framework encourages us to consider which and whose resources (including the body) are accorded value, in what contexts and conditions, and to what effects. Central to this framework is the notion of habitus as embodied scheme engendering ways of thinking and being in line with the (classed, gendered and racialised) relations of its production (Bourdieu 1984). Because of this, when the habitus finds itself in a setting of which it is the product it is like 'a fish in water', seamlessly navigating the world around it (Bourdieu and Wacquant 1992). Yet, in environments marked by discordant (classed, gendered and racialised) cultures, the lack of fit brings about restructuring and potential fractures (Bourdieu 2004). The analysis conducted has illustrated the richness, nuance and complexity of the picture that emerges from this perspective. In particular, as it reveals the range of tensions, adaptations and resistances generated by multiple (mis-)alignments between individuals' habitus and resources, informed by their relative positioning in terms of class, ethnicity, race, religion and gender, and those privileged in the contexts where they engage.

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